

1 Global Deep Ocean Observations of Horizontal
2 Eddy-Mean Interactions of Temperature Variance

3 F. SÉVELLEC*, N. KOŁODZIEJCZYK, A. HOCHET, AND T. HUCK

4 *Laboratoire d'Océanographie Physique et Spatiale, Univ Brest CNRS IRD Ifremer, Brest, France*

5 Submitted to *J. Phys. Oceanogr.* 10 October 2025

6 Revised 11 February 2026 and 8 April 2026

**Corresponding author address:* Laboratoire d'Océanographie Physique et Spatiale, Institut Universitaire Européen de la Mer, Technopôle Brest Iroise, Plouzané, FRANCE. Phone: +33-290-91-5540 email: florian.sevellec@univ-brest.fr

Abstract

8 Ocean eddies are ubiquitous in the ocean. Characterizing and quantifying their impact
9 on the large-scale ocean circulation is key. Here we compute eddy-mean interactions for
10 Conservative Temperature variance, including temperature variance transfers. This is done
11 using the ANDRO dataset, which records mean temperature and horizontal displacement
12 of Argo floats during their journey at parking depth (~ 1000 m). The analysis does not
13 show any consistency between the sign of the turbulent heat flux and the slope of the mean
14 isotherms, questioning the validity of traditional downgradient flux turbulent closure in the
15 context of temperature variance budget. The temperature variance interactions suggest the
16 dominance of the non-local, redistribution term over the local, transfer term. They both
17 have typical spatial scales ranging from 200 km to 1000 km. When averaged over large
18 regions, transfers are from the mean to the turbulence, but the North West Atlantic remains
19 a unique region which acts as a turbulence graveyard. Within a water mass framework,
20 transfers are quite consistently shrinking the mean temperature distribution except for a
21 few extreme Water Masses: the Arctic Intermediate Water, the Antarctic Bottom Water,
22 and the Red Sea – Persian Gulf Intermediate Water. This is also the case for a subset
23 of the Mediterranean Water. However the Mediterranean Water is the main location of
24 the broadening of the mean temperature distribution. These results provide observational
25 evidence of the action of the turbulence on the mean temperature structure that could be
26 tested in numerical ocean and climate models for validation and for the development and
27 the implementation of ocean turbulent closures.

28 1 Introduction

29 Since the preindustrial era, climate is changing at an unrecorded pace (IPCC, 2021). This is
30 true for all its components, including the ocean that has stored 90% of the heat excess (von
31 Schuckmann et al., 2023). This heat changes the large-scale ocean temperature structure.
32 To further anticipate this change, it becomes more and more timely to better understand the
33 dynamics and the physical process controlling this large-scale ocean temperature structure.
34 In parallel, one of the most energetic features, that is ubiquitous in the ocean (Chelton et al.,
35 2007), is the mesoscale eddy turbulence (Ferrari and Wunsch, 2009). Hence understanding
36 how this energetic turbulence and the large-scale temperature structure interact is the central
37 question of this study.

38 There is a long history of studying eddy-mean flow interactions in the fields of ocean
39 and atmospheric research. We could cite the negative viscosity concept of Starr (1968),
40 rationalizing the eddy-driven character of the midlatitude westerlies, or the eddy-forced
41 nature of the inertial recirculation of the Gulf Stream, established by Holland (1978) and
42 Rhines and Holland (1979). Focusing on the temperature, it is well accepted that mean
43 temperature gradients, through their effect on density, contribute to feed eddy turbulence
44 through baroclinic instability (Charney, 1947; Eady, 1949). However this turbulence impacts
45 the temperature field through isopycnal eddy diffusion (McDougall and McIntosh, 2001;
46 McDougall et al., 2014; Groeskamp et al., 2020; Sévellec et al., 2022, 2025b). This is typical
47 evidence of the two-way eddy-mean flow interactions for temperature. However this classical
48 and somehow plausible description remains quite qualitative. A more analytical and robust
49 approach to quantitatively characterize the eddy-mean interactions for temperature is thus
50 required.

51 A robust framework for identifying global-average eddy-mean flow interactions has been
52 developed by Lorenz (1955). This has been extensively used in the oceanographic community
53 to study the interactions between the mean and the eddy Kinetic Energy (e.g., Ferrari
54 and Wunsch, 2009). However, when applied locally, this global framework suffers from an
55 apparent discrepancy between the local gain/loss of the mean energy reservoir and the local
56 loss/gain of the eddy energy reservoir. This has been rationalized through the definition
57 of a ghost reservoir (Residual Kinetic Energy) acting as a mediator between the mean and
58 eddy Kinetic Energy (Murakami, 2011; Murakami et al., 2011; Chen et al., 2014, 2016; Kang
59 and Curchitser, 2015; Yan et al., 2019; Matsuta and Masumoto, 2021; Jamet et al., 2022;
60 Sévellec et al., 2025a). However these studies do not focus on tracers and are thus not
61 directly generalizable to the temperature. Hence, in parallel to these studies there exists
62 a wide range of studies on tracer variance budget (Sévellec et al., 2006; Arzel et al., 2006;
63 Buckley et al., 2012; Hochet et al., 2020; Sévellec et al., 2021; Hochet et al., 2023, 2024b,
64 2026). This framework allows to quantitatively estimate sources and sinks of tracer variance.

65 However these studies are not relating the mean and the eddy temperature. Hochet et al.
66 (2024a) attempted to rationalize the link between mean reservoir gain and loss and eddy
67 reservoir loss and gain, respectively. Whereas their suggestion is perfectly valid for global
68 interpretation, they face the same local issue than the one discussed above for Kinetic Energy.
69 They find an inconsistency between gain and loss of tracer variance by the mean and eddy
70 reservoirs. Hence a consistent framework, analog to the one for Kinetic Energy and valid for
71 local interactions but tailored for temperature, is needed.

72 Indeed there are specific scientific questions and challenges for the temperature bud-
73 get. This could be illustrated by starting from the evolution equation for the Conservative
74 Temperature. This reads:

$$D_t\Theta = F_\Theta + D_\Theta, \quad (1)$$

75 where Θ is the Conservative Temperature (McDougall and Barker, 2011), D_t is the material
76 derivative, and F_Θ and D_Θ are the surface atmospheric forcing and small-scale dissipative
77 terms. The material derivative reads $D_t = \partial_t + \mathbf{u}^\dagger \cdot \nabla$, where t is time, $\mathbf{u}^\dagger = (u, v, w)$ is the
78 three dimensional velocity vector (with u , v , and w being the zonal, meridional, and ver-
79 tical velocities, and $\nabla^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$ ensure the non-divergence of the flow), $\nabla^\dagger = (\partial_x, \partial_y, \partial_z)$ is the
80 three dimensional derivative operator (with x , y , and z being the longitude, latitude, and
81 depth), \cdot is the three dimensional scalar product, and † is the transpose operator. Based on
82 this equation and an *ad hoc* derivation using a water mass framework (Walín, 1982), Zika
83 et al. (2015) suggested that the water masses distribution is controlled by an equilibrium
84 between the forcing term and the dissipation. Indeed, intuitively if the dissipation term is a
85 diffusion, by mixing waters it removes the differences and sharpens the distribution. In the
86 case of diffusion represented by downgradient fluxes, it is indeed trivial. Hence only remains
87 the forcing term to maintain temperature differences and broaden the distribution. This is
88 equivalent to inflection point in Temperature-Salinity diagram due to the “stirring” of water
89 types (i.e., temperature-salinity properties at their origin/formation). However, if one is
90 interested by some kind of spatio-temporal average rather than local/instantaneous value,
91 (1) would be modified to include a turbulent term. Hence all the previous neat arguments
92 would fail if this term was not equivalent to a diffusion characterized by downgradient fluxes.
93 For instance, if the turbulent term acts as a negative diffusivity, similarly to the so-called
94 negative viscosity described by Starr (1968), it would broaden the temperature distribution.
95 To clarify this, in the present study, we will derive the exact equation controlling the broad-
96 ening/sharpening of spatio-temporal average ocean temperature distribution. We will then
97 describe the impact of mesoscale turbulence for the distribution of temperature in the ocean.

98 To this purpose we will use the ANDRO dataset (Ollitrault and Rannou, 2013), that
99 provides concomitant horizontal velocity and temperature observations measured during the
100 deep displacements of Argo floats. To diagnose eddy-mean interactions with this dataset,

101 we will develop a framework describing the interactions between the Mean Temperature
102 Variance and the Eddy Temperature Variance. Equivalently to the description of eddy-
103 mean flow interactions for Kinetic Energy, we will show the existence of local and non-local
104 interactions. The former corresponds to variance transfers, whereas the latter corresponds
105 to variance redistribution. Application of the framework to the dataset shows that the eddy
106 turbulence tends on average to smooth mean temperature differences (as hypothesized by
107 Zika et al., 2015), but not locally.

108 The manuscript is organized as follows. In section 2 the ANDRO dataset is described.
109 In section 3 the theoretical framework is derived and restriction to a horizontal framework
110 is discussed. The results are presented in section 4. We conclude with discussions of our
111 results in section 5.

112 2 The ANDRO dataset

113 In this study, we have used temperature record and velocity estimations from Argo float
114 deep displacements. By using temperature recorded during deep displacements, rather than
115 during vertical profiles, we have consistent observations of temperature and velocities. These
116 observations are provided by the ANDRO dataset (Ollitrault et al., 2025). In particular we
117 used the #116520 release of 2025. It has all the Argo float deep drifts from 2000 to 2009, but
118 is only partially complete for 2010-2025. This dataset corresponds to 1 678 510 observations,
119 but when selecting the studied pressure range (950-1 150 dbar) we find 1 248 238 observations
120 (Fig. 1a). In the rest of the study, we will consider this depth to be $\sim 1\,000$ m. When limiting
121 the range of temperature between -2°C and 13°C (to avoid erroneous data), we obtained
122 1 221 746 observations. This leads to a mean observation density of 144.0 observations per
123 $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ with a standard deviation of 87.9 observations per $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ and a maximum observation
124 density reaching 915 observations per $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ (Fig. 1b).

125 Using these velocity and temperature records we computed the mean of the zonal velocity,
126 meridional velocity, and Conservative Temperature fields, on a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ -grid, as:

$$\bar{u} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n u_i, \quad (2a)$$

$$\bar{v} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n v_i, \quad (2b)$$

$$\bar{\Theta} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \Theta_i, \quad (2c)$$

129 where u_i and v_i are individual deep zonal and meridional velocity records, respectively, Θ_i
130 is individual deep Conservative Temperature record, i is the index of the record, and n is
131 the total number of records within a $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ cell centered on a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid point.

FIGURE 1: Distribution of velocity observations from the ANDRO dataset. (a) Distributions of the parking depth pressure of the Argo float deep displacements from the ANDRO dataset (#116520). Two sequential selections of observations: P -selection corresponding to a range of pressure (from 950 dbar to 1150 dbar) and $P\&\Theta$ -selection corresponding to both the range of pressure and a range of Conservative Temperature (from -2°C to 13°C). (b) Number of $P\&\Theta$ -selected deep velocities observations per $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$. Note the logarithmic color scale.

132 We can also compute the unbiased variance of these fields:

$$\overline{u'^2} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (u_i - \bar{u})^2, \quad (3a)$$

133

$$\overline{v'^2} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (v_i - \bar{v})^2, \quad (3b)$$

134

$$\overline{\Theta'^2} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (\Theta_i - \bar{\Theta})^2. \quad (3c)$$

135 An estimation of the deep horizontal Mean and Eddy Kinetic Energy can then be obtained
 136 as $\text{MKE} = (\bar{u}^2 + \bar{v}^2)/2$ and $\text{EKE} = (\overline{u'^2} + \overline{v'^2})/2$.

137 Following the same principle, we define the unbiased covariance of the zonal and merid-
 138 ional velocity with the Conservative Temperature. This reads:

$$\overline{u'\Theta'} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (u_i - \bar{u}) (\Theta_i - \bar{\Theta}), \quad (4a)$$

$$\overline{v'\Theta'} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (v_i - \bar{v}) (\Theta_i - \bar{\Theta}). \quad (4b)$$

141 At 1000 m, we find mean Conservative Temperature going from -1.8°C in the Nordic
 142 Seas to 11.8°C along the Portugal coast and in the Gulf of Aden (Fig. 2a). In the Southern
 143 Ocean we obtained water down to 0.5°C , whereas it is 2.5°C and 3.3°C in the Pacific and
 144 the Atlantic, respectively. This is consistent with state-of-the-art knowledge of descriptive
 145 oceanography (Talley et al., 2011). Following Emery (2018), we find a range of water masses
 146 at this depth: the Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW), the Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW),
 147 the Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), the Mediterranean Water (MW), the Red Sea
 148 – Persian Gulf Intermediate Water (RSPGIW), the North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW),
 149 and the Arctic Intermediate Water (AIW). The temperature variance shows value of up to
 150 3 K^2 , localized in the Agulhas retroflection and return current, in the Gulf Stream and its
 151 continuation as the North Atlantic Current, in the Antarctic Circumpolar Current, and in
 152 the North Brazilian Current retroflection (Fig. 2b). In terms of momentum, the Mean and
 153 Eddy Kinetic Energy (MKE and EKE) have values of up to $10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$,
 154 respectively. They are strong in intense western boundary currents (*e.g.*, Gulf Stream,
 155 Kuroshio, Zapiola Gyre, and Agulhas Current and its retroflection), as well as in the ACC
 156 (Fig. 2c and d). EKE is also strong in the equatorial region. This was already reported with
 157 an older version of the same dataset (#109566) by Sévellec et al. (2025a).

158 Using error estimates of the individual velocities provided by the ANDRO dataset (Ol-
 159 litrault et al., 2025), full error estimation has been provided in Sévellec et al. (2024) and
 160 Sévellec et al. (2025a). This includes observation error (primarily controlled by the Argo
 161 float positioning error at 1000 dbar), sample size error, and error introduced by the grid-scale
 162 choice of the analysis. We refer the readers to these two studies for details. Overall, these
 163 error estimations show the robustness of analyses based on mean and variance. This directly
 164 derives from the high number of individual observations within $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ -cells (Fig. 1) and the
 165 good convergence of the simple statistics, such as the mean and the variance. As in Sévellec
 166 et al. (2024) and Sévellec et al. (2025a), in the rest of the study, we will only use mean and
 167 variance. It is also worth noting that despite being Lagrangian observations the ANDRO
 168 dataset has been shown to lead to results consistent with Eulerian analyses, as for isopycnal
 169 diffusivity coefficient estimate (Sévellec et al., 2022, vs Roach et al., 2018, and Groeskamp
 170 et al., 2020), for instance.

FIGURE 2: Conservative Temperature and Kinetic Energy from Argo float deep displacement observations at 1000-m depth. (a) Mean Conservative Temperature ($\bar{\Theta}$), (b) Conservative Temperature variance ($\overline{\Theta'^2}$), (c) Mean Kinetic Energy [$\text{MKE} = (\bar{u}^2 + \bar{v}^2)/2$], and (d) Eddy Kinetic Energy [$\text{EKE} = (\overline{u'^2} + \overline{v'^2})/2$]. The observations have been mapped following (2) and (3). The black line and boxes denote the regions used for spatial averages: West, Central, East, and all North Atlantic, Agulhas Current sector, and Southern Ocean sector.

171 3 Theoretical framework

172 a. General derivations of temperature variance budget

173 Restarting from (1) and applying the change of variable $T = \Theta - \langle \Theta \rangle$ (where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is a spatio-
 174 temporal average defined over the whole globe and over the full duration of the studied
 175 time-series), we obtain the time evolution equation for the centered temperature:

$$D_t T = F + D, \quad (5)$$

176 where F and D derived from F_Θ and D_Θ , respectively, but have been adapted for the change
 177 of variable. Note that $D \equiv D_\Theta$, if D_Θ has the form of a Laplacian. Also, note that, if
 178 the average is only a horizontal and temporal average ($\langle \cdot \rangle_{\text{hor}}$), defining a mean stratified
 179 reference state, as often done in the context of Available Potential Energy definition (e.g,
 180 Lorenz, 1955), we have $\partial_z \langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}} \neq 0$ and the forcing F should incorporate a term of the form
 181 $-w \partial_z \langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}}$ deriving from the advective term (and potentially a term deriving from the
 182 diffusive term, although it is often negligible, since the Péclet number is high – $\text{Pe} \gg 1$). This
 183 property will be used in section 4d..

184 From (5) and splitting the temperature and velocity in a statistical mean and an anomaly
 185 so that $T = \bar{T} + T'$ and $\mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{u}'$, where $\bar{T}' = 0$ and $\bar{\mathbf{u}}' = (0, 0, 0)$, we obtain the evolution equation
 186 for the mean and anomalous centered temperature:

$$\partial_t \bar{T} + \nabla^\dagger \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{u}} \bar{T}) = \underbrace{-\nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}' T'}}_c + \bar{F} + \bar{D}, \quad (6a)$$

$$\partial_t T' + \nabla^\dagger \cdot (\mathbf{u} T') = -\nabla^\dagger \cdot (\mathbf{u}' \bar{T}) + \underbrace{\nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}' T'}}_{-c} + F' + D'. \quad (6b)$$

187 where $\overline{\mathbf{u}' T'} = (\overline{u' T'}, \overline{v' T'}, \overline{w' T'})$ is the turbulent temperature flux. (Note that $T' = \Theta'$.) This
 188 shows the importance of the divergence of the turbulent temperature flux ($\overline{\mathbf{u}' T'}$) in forcing
 189 the mean temperature. This term could also be interpreted as the closure term for the large
 190 scale evolution: $\mathcal{C} = -\nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}' T'}$.

192 To study the variance, we define three temperature variance reservoirs: the Mean, the
 193 Residual, and the Eddy Temperature Variance reservoirs, so that $\text{MTV} = \bar{T}^2$, $\overline{\text{RTV}} = 2\bar{T} T' = 0$,
 194 and $\overline{\text{ETV}} = \overline{T'^2}$ (Fig. 3). This decomposition directly derived from $T^2 = \bar{T}^2 + 2\bar{T} T' + \overline{T'^2}$. This
 195 corresponds to the zeroth, first, and second order anomaly of the temperature square. It
 196 is worth noting that residual reservoir is identical to zero on average, and could then be
 197 considered has a “ghost” reservoir. However as shown latter, and in analogy with the work
 198 of Chen et al. (2014, 2016) in the context of Kinetic and Potential Energy, it is key as RTV
 199 acts as a mediator between ETV and MTV. From multiplying (6) with either \bar{T} or T' , we
 200 obtain the evolution of these three temperature variance reservoirs. This leads to:

$$\partial_t \bar{T}^2 + \nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u} \bar{T}^2} = \underbrace{-2\bar{T} \nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}' T'}}_{\mathcal{R}=\mathcal{A}+\mathcal{T}} + 2\bar{T} \bar{F} + 2\bar{T} \bar{D}, \quad (7a)$$

$$\partial_t \underbrace{2\overline{\overline{T}T'}}_{=0} + \underbrace{\nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}2\overline{\overline{T}T'}}}_{-\mathcal{A}} = \underbrace{2\overline{\overline{T}\nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}}}_{-\mathcal{R}} + \underbrace{2(\nabla\overline{T})^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}}_{\mathcal{T}} + \underbrace{2\overline{\overline{T}(F'+D')}}_{=0} + \underbrace{2\overline{\overline{T}'(\overline{F}+\overline{D})}}_{=0}, \quad (7b)$$

$$\partial_t \overline{\overline{T}^2} + \nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}T'^2} = \underbrace{-2(\nabla\overline{T})^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}}_{-\mathcal{T}} + 2\overline{\overline{T}'F'} + 2\overline{\overline{T}'D'}. \quad (7c)$$

201 Here we find that the eddy-mean interactions, $\mathcal{R} = -2\overline{\overline{T}\nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}}$, is the sum of the variance
 202 redistribution, $\mathcal{A} = -2\nabla^\dagger \cdot (\overline{\overline{T}\mathbf{u}'T'})$, and the variance transfers, $\mathcal{T} = 2(\nabla\overline{T})^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}$. Following
 203 analog work done on eddy-mean flow interactions for the Kinetic Energy reservoirs (Chen
 204 et al., 2014, 2016; Sévellec et al., 2025a), we also define \mathcal{R} , \mathcal{A} , and \mathcal{T} as the total, non-local,
 205 and local interactions (Fig. 3). In (7) we see the special role of advection for RTV (\mathcal{A}).
 206 Indeed for MTV and ETV, their respective advection only acts as an intra-reservoir action.
 207 However for RTV, because RTV is unambiguously zero on average, this intra-reservoir action
 208 impacts the inter-reservoir interactions and accumulates with \mathcal{T} from ETV to impact MTV
 209 through \mathcal{R} .
 210

211 Equivalent derivations have been done in the context of energy reservoir exchange of
 212 Available Potential Energy ($\propto \rho^2$, where ρ is density) by Kang and Curchitser (2015) and
 213 Chen et al. (2016) and of potential energy in a quasi-geostrophic model [$\propto (\partial_z \psi)^2$, where ψ is
 214 the streamfunction] by Jamet et al. (2024), for instance. These derivations lead to equivalent
 215 eddy-mean interaction terms and reservoirs.

216 From (7) we can retrieve the more classical global view (equivalent to the Lorenz, 1955,
 217 energy cycle) by integrating over the volume of the ocean. This reads:

$$\partial_t \iiint_V \overline{\overline{T}}^2 dv = 2 \iiint_V (\nabla\overline{T})^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'} dv + 2 \iiint_V (\overline{\overline{T}\overline{F}} + \overline{\overline{T}\overline{D}}) dv, \quad (8a)$$

$$\partial_t \iiint_V \overline{\overline{T}^2} dv = -2 \iiint_V (\nabla\overline{T})^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'} dv + 2 \iiint_V (\overline{\overline{T}'F'} + \overline{\overline{T}'D'}) dv, \quad (8b)$$

218 where V is the total ocean volume and dv is the volume element. Here we only need two
 219 reservoirs: the global-mean MTV and ETV. Also, beyond forcing and dissipation, only
 220 the eddy-mean interactions remain, since advection terms vanish when globally averaged
 221 (as a consequence of mass conservation). Finally, the eddy-mean interactions simplify to
 222 $\iiint_V \mathcal{R} dv = \iiint_V \mathcal{T} dv$, since $\iiint_V \mathcal{A} dv = 0$ (again, as a consequence of mass conservation), lead-
 223 ing to non-ambiguous variance transfers between the mean and the eddy reservoirs. Also
 224 $\iiint_V \mathcal{R} dv$ is a direct contributor to the variance of the temperature distribution, showing
 225 the impact of the turbulence on the temperature distribution. Indeed dividing by the global
 226 volume, (8a) becomes an equation for the spatial-variance of the large-scale temperature
 227 ($\sigma_{\overline{\overline{T}}}^2 = \langle \overline{\overline{T}}^2 \rangle$). This reads:

$$\partial_t \sigma_{\overline{\overline{T}}}^2 = \langle \mathcal{T} \rangle + 2 \langle \overline{\overline{T}\overline{F}} \rangle + 2 \langle \overline{\overline{T}\overline{D}} \rangle. \quad (9)$$

228 This derivation was also provided in the context of freshwater content variation of the Arctic
 229 by Hochet et al. (2024a), for instance. In this expression, the forcing term acts as the
 230

TEMPERATURE VARIANCE RESERVOIR INTERACTIONS

GLOBAL VIEW:

LOCAL VIEW:

FIGURE 3: Schematic of global and local interactions between temperature variance reservoirs. Globally, variance transfers are from Eddy Temperature Variance ($\overline{ETV} = \overline{T'^2}$) to Mean Temperature Variance ($MTV = \bar{T}^2$) through the intra-reservoir action of the spatial integral of the eddy-mean interactions, solely controlled by the local component (*i.e.*, $\iiint_V \mathcal{R} dv = \iiint_V \mathcal{T} dv$). Locally, variance transfers occur both through the intra-reservoir action of advection and through the inter-reservoir action of the eddy-mean interactions. Here, the reservoirs are the Mean Temperature Variance ($MTV = \bar{T}^2$), the Residual Temperature Variance ($\overline{RTV} = 2\bar{T}\bar{T}' = 0$), and the Eddy Temperature Variance ($\overline{ETV} = \overline{T'^2}$). The eddy-mean interactions correspond to the total component (\mathcal{R}) received by Mean Temperature Variance, the local component (\mathcal{T}) leaving the mean Eddy Temperature Variance, and the non-local component (\mathcal{A}) leaving the mean Residual Temperature Variance and ensuring that it remains zero at all time despite the existence of RTV eddy-advection. By construction the total component is the sum of the local and non-local components ($\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{A} + \mathcal{T}$).

231 spatial-covariance between temperature forcing and the mean temperature field. Hence,
 232 beyond the amplitude, the shape consistency between the temperature forcing and the mean
 233 temperature, is key in modifying the spatial-variance of the large-scale temperature.

234 At high Péclet number ($Pe \gg 1$ – diffusion is negligible over advection: $\langle \bar{T} \bar{D} \rangle \simeq 0$) the
 235 distribution is maintained (i.e., $\partial_t \sigma_{\bar{T}}^2 = 0$) by a balance between the forcing and the action of
 236 the turbulence:

$$\langle \bar{T} \bar{F} \rangle = -\frac{1}{2} \langle \mathcal{T} \rangle. \quad (10)$$

237 This is the analytical demonstration of the intuitive description of the maintenance and
 238 broadening of the ocean’s tracer distribution suggested by Zika et al. (2015), who only
 239 proposed an advanced scaling argument.

240 Even if not of leading order locally (i.e., $Pe \gg 1$), it is possible that the global impact
 241 of the diffusive term is key. The small-scale dissipative term is often assumed to take the
 242 form of a downgradient flux – Fick’s law (Redi, 1982): $D = \nabla^\dagger \cdot (\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla \bar{T})$, where \mathbf{K} is the
 243 diffusivity tensor. This diffusivity tensor is positively defined as it measures the spread in
 244 time of Lagrangian trajectories (Batchelor, 1949; Sévellec et al., 2022), which can only grow
 245 statistically. In this case it can be shown that the global impact of this term on the mean
 246 temperature variance reads:

$$\langle \bar{T} \bar{D} \rangle = \frac{1}{V} \iiint_V \bar{T} \nabla^\dagger \cdot (\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla \bar{T}) \, dv = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2V} \oint_{\Sigma} \boldsymbol{\eta}^\dagger \cdot (\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla \bar{T}^2) \, d\sigma}_{=0} - \underbrace{\frac{1}{V} \iiint_V (\nabla \bar{T})^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot (\nabla \bar{T}) \, dv}_{\leq 0},$$

247 where Σ is the surface bounding the ocean, $d\sigma$ is its surface ocean boundary element, and
 248 $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ is the vector normal to this surface. Given that the forcing has been explicitly expressed
 249 through F , the variance flux is zero. Since it is a scalar product using a positive definite
 250 tensor, the second term is unequivocally lower than or equal to zero at all locations: $-(\nabla \bar{T})^\dagger \cdot$
 251 $\mathbf{K} \cdot (\nabla \bar{T}) \leq 0$, and so also when globally averaged. Hence, here, we demonstrate that, under
 252 the Fick’s law assumption, the small-scale dissipative term leads to the shrinking of the mean
 253 temperature distribution ($\partial_t \sigma_{\bar{T}}^2 \leq 0$), as also suggested by Zika et al. (2015) in a water mass
 254 transformation framework. Physically, this means that the diffusion is mixing water until
 255 there only exists a single temperature class.

256 Equivalently to the variance of the mean temperature, we can define the mean variance
 257 of the anomaly: $\langle \sigma_{T'}^2 \rangle = \overline{\langle T'^2 \rangle}$. Using (8b), its evolution is described by:

$$\partial_t \langle \sigma_{T'}^2 \rangle = -\langle \mathcal{T} \rangle + 2 \langle T' F' \rangle + 2 \langle T' D' \rangle. \quad (11)$$

258 This equation has already been derived in the context of the large-scale ocean variabil-
 259 ity by Sévellec et al. (2006), for instance. The same properties can be derived for this
 260 mean variance as for the variance of the mean. (1) The forcing acts through the global

261 mean of the correlation between forcing anomaly and the temperature anomaly. (2) Small-
 262 scale dissipation can only be a sink of variance if one assumes a downgradient flux closure:
 263 $\langle T'D' \rangle = -\langle (\nabla T')^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot (\nabla T') \rangle \leq 0$. However, scaling analysis suggests that $\langle \mathcal{T} \rangle \sim \lambda^{-1}$ and
 264 $\langle T'D' \rangle \sim \lambda^{-2}$, where λ is the typical length-scale of the studied process. Hence, for small
 265 scale processes, diffusion can become of order one ($\text{Pe} \simeq 1$) or even leading order ($\text{Pe} > 1$).
 266 This means that at equilibrium (i.e., $\partial_t \langle \sigma_{T'}^2 \rangle = 0$) the small-scale dissipative term plays a role
 267 in the balance of the mean variance of the anomaly.

268 *b. Restriction to a horizontal framework*

269 Since we only have access to horizontal velocity (section 2) we restrict our study to horizontal
 270 interactions and adapt the general derivations of section 3a.. First we redefine T as the
 271 difference between the observed temperature and its horizontal global mean. With this
 272 definition T is the departure from the mean at ~ 1000 m, showing regions warmer and colder
 273 than the mean and thus the spatial structure of the temperature at this depth. In this context
 274 it is similar to the Available Potential Energy (APE, Lorenz, 1955), where for our reference
 275 depth, there is regions with higher and lower density (colder and warmer) and so higher and
 276 lower APE, respectively. For the impact of turbulent flow on the mean temperature we have
 277 only $\mathcal{C}|_{\text{hor}} = -\nabla_H^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}$, where $\mathbf{u}'_H = (u, v)$ is the two dimensional horizontal velocity vector,
 278 $\nabla_H^\dagger = (\partial_x, \partial_y)$ is the two dimensional horizontal derivative operator, and \cdot now represents the
 279 two dimensional scalar product.

280 For the impact on the temperature variance within a horizontal restricted framework we
 281 obtain:

$$282 \quad \mathcal{R}|_{\text{hor}} = -2\bar{T} \nabla_H^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}, \quad (12a)$$

$$283 \quad \mathcal{A}|_{\text{hor}} = -2 \nabla_H^\dagger \cdot (\bar{T} \overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}), \quad (12b)$$

$$284 \quad \mathcal{T}|_{\text{hor}} = 2 (\nabla_H \bar{T})^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}. \quad (12c)$$

285 Key properties of the eddy-mean interactions still remain even when focusing on the
 286 horizontal components, though. Hence, when globally averaged the horizontal component of
 287 the non-local eddy-mean interaction component reads:

$$288 \quad \iint_S \mathcal{A}|_{\text{hor}} ds = -2 \iint_S \nabla_H^\dagger \cdot (\overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T' \bar{T}}) ds = -2 \oint_L \overline{(\mathbf{n}^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{u}'_H) T' \bar{T}} dl \simeq 0, \quad (13)$$

289 where S and L define the ocean surface and boundary at the studied depth, respectively, ds
 290 and dl define their surface and length elements, and \mathbf{n} is the vector normal to the boundary.
 291 Hence, $\mathbf{n}^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{u}'_H$ is the projection of the horizontal turbulent flow on normal-boundary vector,
 292 which is close to 0 assuming strong boundary slope and because of mass conservation (i.e.,
 no mass is transported through the boundary). This means that, even when focusing on the

293 horizontal component, the global average of the non-local component is still close to 0: there
 294 is weak net global eddy transport of residual temperature variance. As a consequence, the
 295 local and total components become almost equal:

$$\iint_S \mathcal{R}|_{\text{hor}} ds \simeq \iint_S \mathcal{T}|_{\text{hor}} ds. \quad (14)$$

296 Hence, even when focusing on the horizontal components if assuming strong boundary slope,
 297 loss and gain of mean variance are almost equivalent to gain and loss of eddy variance,
 298 allowing the unequivocal interpretation of total/local global-mean components as variance
 299 transfers. As a global average, this term is the forcing term of the spatial variance of the
 300 mean temperature field. It shows how the turbulent flux maintains or destroys, depending
 301 of the sign, the large-scale structure of the conservative temperature. Hence it measures the
 302 ability of the turbulence to broaden or sharpen the conservative temperature distribution.

303 The reason for only focusing on the horizontal components of the transfers is a direct
 304 consequence of the dataset limitation. However we can still estimate the relative error
 305 of this constraint. Colin de Verdière and Tailleux (2005) and Sévellec and Huck (2016)
 306 have suggested the existence of an adimensional number (ϵ) that measures the ratio of the
 307 horizontal advection to the vertical one. It derives from the advection equation of neutral
 308 density under the assumptions of geostrophic and hydrostatic balances. This reads:

$$\epsilon = \left| \frac{f}{h\beta} \frac{\|\nabla_H \gamma\|}{\partial_z \gamma} \right|, \quad (15)$$

309 where γ is the neutral density, f is the Coriolis parameter, $\beta = \partial_y f$ is the meridional variation
 310 of the Coriolis parameter due to the Earth’s curvature, $\|\nabla_H \gamma\| = \sqrt{(\nabla_H \bar{\gamma})^\dagger \cdot (\nabla_H \bar{\gamma})}$ is the
 311 neutral density horizontal gradient amplitude, and h is the pycnocline depth. The relative
 312 importance of horizontal and vertical advection has been reinterpreted by Sévellec and Huck
 313 (2015). They suggest the dominance of baroclinic instabilities in the horizontal “regime”
 314 ($\epsilon \gg 1$) and the dominance of baroclinic Rossby waves in the vertical “regime” ($\epsilon \ll 1$).

315 To estimate ϵ we have used the ISAS17 product (Kolodziejczyk et al., 2023) which pro-
 316 vides temperature and salinity gridded fields from an Optimal Interpolation (Bretherton
 317 et al., 1976; Gaillard et al., 2016) of Argo profiles. The neutral density was computed
 318 through the Gibbs SeaWater Oceanographic Toolbox of TEOS-10 code. The estimation
 319 of the depth of the pycnocline was based on a scaling argument (i.e., typical depth of the
 320 pycnocline). Also, studied turbulent processes are necessarily reaching the depth of the
 321 measurement. Hence we set $h = 1\,000$ m.

322 Computing the adimensional number ϵ (Fig. 4), we find that the horizontal regime is
 323 dominant poleward of the mid-latitudes (i.e., north of 35°N and south of 35°S). In particular
 324 the ACC is largely in this horizontal regime, whereas the Gulf Stream and its eastward
 325 continuation as the North Atlantic Current, the Kuroshio, the Agulhas Current, and the

326 Zapiola Gyre are marginally but still in this horizontal regime. On the other hand subtropical
 327 and equatorial regions are in the vertical regime. (Note that the scaling is not informative at
 328 the equator because the geostrophic balance is invalid there.) As it will be shown later, this
 329 suggests that key regions for turbulent temperature flux, for mean temperature gradient,
 330 and for eddy-mean interactions are primarily within horizontal regime.

FIGURE 4: Ratio of horizontal to vertical dynamics in log scale, following (15). The ratio (ϵ) measures the propensity of the advection equation to be dominated by horizontal advection ($\epsilon \gg 1$) or by vertical advection ($\epsilon \ll 1$) under the geostrophic balance assumption. The former regime is more inductive to baroclinic instabilities, whereas the latter regime is more inductive to baroclinic Rossby waves. The thick black contour corresponds to the perfect balance (i.e., $\epsilon=1$).

331 Beyond this dynamical regime argument, it is worth noting that, in our framework, part
 332 of the temperature stratification has been included in a background reservoir (by removing
 333 $\langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}}$). Hence it is not acting, *per se*, within the temperature interaction terms, but as a
 334 background source for the mean temperature variance. This further limits the importance of
 335 the vertical motion as it is restricted to $w \partial_z T$, instead of $w \partial_z \Theta$. The difference ($\partial_z \langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}}$) is
 336 fully acknowledged in our framework and will be used later to estimate the optimal vertical
 337 velocity (see section 4d.).

338 **4 Results**

339 *a. Data properties*

340 Based on the previous section, rather than focusing on zonal and meridional components,
 341 we define the turbulent temperature fluxes with respect to the Conservative Temperature
 342 horizontal gradient. Looking at the gradient amplitude ($\|\nabla_H \bar{T}\|$), we find that it is intense
 343 along intense currents (Fig. 5). We can identify the regions of western boundary currents,
 344 such as the Gulf Stream and the Kuroshio, as well as of the ACC. An important temperature
 345 gradient is also visible in the Eastern part of the North Atlantic. This is created by the
 346 Mediterranean Water as it spreads into the cooler North Atlantic. Averaged over our 2° -
 347 cells, we find values of the mean temperature gradient of the order of several 10^{-6} K m^{-1}
 348 and up to $4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K m}^{-1}$.

FIGURE 5: Amplitude of the horizontal mean temperature gradient ($\|\nabla_H \bar{T}\|$).

349 Based on this mean temperature gradient we compute the turbulent flux along and across
 350 isotherms. This reads:

$$\overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}_{\parallel} = \overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'} \times \frac{\nabla_H \bar{T}}{\|\nabla_H \bar{T}\|}, \quad (16a)$$

$$\overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}_{\perp} = \overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}^{\dagger} \cdot \frac{\nabla_H \bar{T}}{\|\nabla_H \bar{T}\|}, \quad (16b)$$

352 where \times is the two dimensional vector product, and \parallel and \perp denote the along and across
 353 isothermal directions, respectively. We find that the two components are both impor-

354 tant (Fig. 6). This means that there is turbulent fluxes both across and along the mean-
 355 temperature gradient. These fluxes reach values from a few to several 10^{-2} K m s $^{-1}$ with
 356 a maximum absolute value of 0.15 K m s $^{-1}$. Focusing on the along isothermal component,
 357 we find consistent patterns that are elongated along isotherms. They are particularly strong
 358 along the Gulf Stream, the Kuroshio, and the ACC. For all three of these currents the along-
 359 isothermal turbulent flux corresponds to a positive term to the south and negative term to the
 360 north of the mean temperature gradient amplitude maximum (Fig. 5). Focusing on the across
 361 isothermal component, while the most intense patterns are still in intense boundary current
 362 and within the ACC, they also exist in the East North Atlantic (at the edge between the
 363 Mediterranean Water and the North Atlantic Deep Water). This region is quite consistently
 364 negative. Only 55% of the cross-isothermal turbulent temperature flux is Θ -downgradient
 365 (i.e., $\overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}|_{\perp} < 0$). This suggests that typical diffusivity closure (i.e., Fick's law, Redi, 1982)
 366 will miss almost half of the fluxes if reconstructed by down-gradient flux of mean temper-
 367 ature. Note that this is potentially not problematic for the mean-temperature evolution
 368 [i.e., \mathcal{C} in (6)], as only the divergent part of the flux is key (Appendix, Marshall and Shutts,
 369 1981; Fox-Kemper et al., 2003). Following the same principle, we find that only 46% of the
 370 cross-isopycnal turbulent temperature flux is γ -downgradient (i.e., $\overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'} \cdot \nabla_H \bar{\gamma} / \|\nabla_H \bar{\gamma}\| < 0$).
 371 Overall, turbulent fluxes appear strong within regions of intense currents.

372 To estimate the impact of the turbulent flux onto the mean-temperature evolution we
 373 compute its divergence (i.e., $\mathcal{C}|_{\text{hor}} = -\nabla_H^{\dagger} \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}$). We find that the fluxes are of the order
 374 of several 10^{-8} K s $^{-1}$ (~ 1 K in 3 years), with a maximum absolute value of 5×10^{-7} K s $^{-1}$
 375 (Fig. 7). The divergence of the turbulent flux occurs mainly within intense boundary cur-
 376 rents and shows a succession of positive and negative values corresponding to warming and
 377 cooling of the mean-temperature by the turbulence, respectively. The typical spatial-scale
 378 corresponds to consistent pattern of a few to several degrees.

379 To estimate regional impacts of the flux divergence we compute its mean globally and
 380 over 6 active regions: the whole North Atlantic – 80°W-0° and 25°N-60°N, the Western
 381 North Atlantic – 80°W-46°W and 25°N-60°N, the Central North Atlantic – 46°W-30°W and
 382 25°N-60°N, the Eastern North Atlantic – 30°W-0° and 25°N-60°N, the Agulhas Current
 383 sector – 10°E-90°E and 55°S-20°S, and the Southern Ocean sector – south of 35°S (as shown
 384 in Fig. 2a). This shows that the regional effect depends on the region considered (Tab. 1).
 385 At the studied depth, globally the turbulence tends to warm the mean temperature by
 386 3.9×10^{-11} K s $^{-1}$ (~ 1 K per millenia). This warming tendency is also true for the whole
 387 North Atlantic and its Western sub-region. The turbulence of the western North Atlantic
 388 leads to a warming of ~ 1 K per century. It is the most intense average temperature changes
 389 that we have identified over the 6 tested regions. Indeed, the Central North Atlantic is
 390 more neutral, with only a slight warming on average (100 times as low as the West North

FIGURE 6: Horizontal turbulent temperature flux. Flux projected (a) along conservative isotherms $(\overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}_{\parallel})$ and (b) across conservative isotherms $(\overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}_{\perp})$, following (16). Contours show mean Conservative Temperature with contours from -2°C to 13°C with 1.5° contour interval.

TURBULENT TEMPERATURE FLUX DIVERGENCE

FIGURE 7: Horizontal divergence of the horizontal turbulent temperature flux ($C|_{\text{hor}} = -\nabla_H^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}$). This term corresponds to the horizontal components of the closure term (*i.e.*, the impact of the turbulence) for the mean temperature, following (6a).

391 Atlantic). On the other hand, turbulence in the east North Atlantic, the Agulhas sector, and
 392 the Southern Ocean sector all tends to cool the mean temperature. It is the most intense in
 393 the Southern Ocean sector, with an average cooling of ~ 1 K per 150 years.

TABLE 1: Spatial-averages of turbulent temperature flux divergence both at global and regional level ($C|_{\text{hor}} = -\nabla_H^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}$). The 6 regions (Fig. 2a) correspond to: the whole North Atlantic (80°W - 0° and 25°N - 60°N), the Western North Atlantic (80°W - 46°W and 25°N - 60°N), the Central North Atlantic (46°W - 30°W and 25°N - 60°N), the Eastern North Atlantic (30°W - 0° and 25°N - 60°N), the Agulhas Current sector (10°E - 90°E and 55°S - 20°S), and the Southern Ocean sector (south of 35°S). Consistently with (6a), positive and negative values correspond to positive and negative trend of the mean temperature, respectively.

$10^{-11} \text{ K s}^{-1}$	Global	North Atlantic			Agulhas	Southern	
	Mean	All	West	Central	East	Current	Ocean
Total	3.9	6.8	34.4	0.3	-15.5	-12.5	-21.2

394 *b. Horizontal eddy-mean interactions*

395 Now that the overall mean and turbulent states have been described, we focus on the three
 396 interactions terms: total, non-local (or variance redistribution) and local (or variance trans-
 397 fers), following (7) and their horizontal expression (12). Our estimations suggest values of
 398 the order of a few $10^{-7} \text{ K}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}$ for the total and non-local term and of several $10^{-8} \text{ K}^2 \text{ m}^{-1}$
 399 for the local term (Fig. 8). We find that 88% of the ocean is dominated by the non-local term
 400 over the local one ($\mathcal{A}|_{\text{hor}}$ vs $\mathcal{T}|_{\text{hor}}$). This is quite interesting as we know that on global scale
 401 the redistribution vanishes. This result is consistent with the one for momentum transfer
 402 (i.e., Kinetic Energy) where similar dominance was found (Sévellec et al., 2025a). Looking at
 403 the residual [i.e., $\mathcal{R}|_{\text{hor}} - (\mathcal{A}|_{\text{hor}} + \mathcal{T}|_{\text{hor}})$] as a proxy for the diagnostic error of the eddy-mean
 404 interactions, we find that this term remains small, even compared to the local term (Fig. 8d).

FIGURE 8: Components of the horizontal eddy-mean interactions for the temperature variance: (a) total ($\mathcal{R}|_{\text{hor}}$), (b) non-local ($\mathcal{A}|_{\text{hor}}$), (c) local ($\mathcal{T}|_{\text{hor}}$), and (d) residual ($\mathcal{R}|_{\text{hor}} - \mathcal{A}|_{\text{hor}} - \mathcal{T}|_{\text{hor}}$), following (12). The residual should be equal to 0 and so measures the estimation error of the eddy-mean interactions. Note the different colorscales for (a) and (b) vs (c) and (d). Positive and negative values correspond to variance transfers from ETV to MTV and from MTV to ETV, respectively.

405 The regions of strong interactions are mainly associated with regions of strong temper-

406 ature variance rather than of strong eddy kinetic energy (Fig. 2). They correspond to the
 407 North Atlantic along the Gulf Stream and its associated North Atlantic Current, the Agulhas
 408 Current, and, but more moderately, the ACC (Fig. 8). The total and non-local terms have
 409 also a signature along the east coast of Africa and along the equator in the Indian Ocean
 410 (Fig. 8a and b). As expected from its expression ($\mathcal{T}|_{\text{hor}}=2\overline{\mathbf{u}'_H T'}|_{\perp}\|\nabla_H \bar{T}\|$) the local term
 411 is the projection of turbulent flux onto the mean temperature gradient (Fig. 8c *vs* Figs. 5
 412 and 6b). Here the inconsistency between the observed turbulent flux and the downgradi-
 413 ent closure becomes obvious and is potentially dramatic for temperature variance transfers.
 414 Indeed the existence of $\mathcal{T}|_{\text{hor}}>0$ is directly related to the upgradient flux (regardless of the
 415 rotational term) and requires negative diffusivity coefficients for the Fick's law to be applied
 416 (Appendix). Hence at the $2^{\circ}\times 2^{\circ}$ -scale and for temperature variance budget, the observed
 417 variance transfers questions the validity of traditional downgradient flux turbulent closure
 418 (Redi, 1982) and the use and estimations of positive diffusivity coefficients (e.g., Klocker and
 419 Abernathey, 2014; Groeskamp et al., 2020; Roach et al., 2018; Sévellec et al., 2022).

420 Focusing on the two key regions: the North Atlantic and the Agulhas Current sector (as
 421 defined above), we see again that the non-local term is almost 4 times as large as the local one
 422 (Fig. 9). However patterns are more spatially-consistent for the local term than for the non-
 423 local term. Indeed the total and non-local terms show positive and negative values of typical
 424 spatial-scale of $\sim 5^{\circ}$, whereas the local term shows values which extend over almost $\sim 10^{\circ}$.
 425 In particular, in the eastern North Atlantic, the local term is almost exclusively negative,
 426 with the core of the pattern extending over $\sim 15^{\circ}$ in both longitudes and latitudes. This
 427 suggests a region of intense variance transfers from the mean temperature to the turbulent
 428 one. We hypothesize that this region of (mostly) downgradient thermal turbulence is linked
 429 to “free” mesoscale turbulence (away from its formation in the Gulf Stream), consistent with
 430 (positive) trajectory dispersion (Taylor, 1921; Batchelor, 1949).

431 When globally-averaged the total interaction is negative with the expected dominance
 432 of the local term (Tab. 2). This suggests that variance is transferred from the mean to
 433 the turbulence. Looking at the 6 key regions (already defined above), the spatial-averages
 434 reveal that most regions are prone to negative interaction (i.e., destruction of the mean
 435 temperature structure) except for the west North Atlantic (Tab. 2). In this region the mean
 436 temperature structure is maintained whereas the temperature turbulence is decreased. In
 437 the west North Atlantic, Agulhas Current, and Southern Ocean the variance redistribution
 438 remains as intense as the variance transfer. This is consistent with region of intense current
 439 where advection plays a crucial role in redistributing variance. In all tested regions and
 440 globally the residual term is weak, suggesting the robustness of the computed diagnostics.

FIGURE 9: As Fig. 8 but zoomed for two key regions, (a, c, and e) the west and east North Atlantic sectors and (b, d, and f) the Agulhas Current sector. Components of the horizontal eddy-mean interactions for the temperature variance: (a-b) total ($\mathcal{R}|_{\text{hor}}$), (c-d) non-local ($\mathcal{A}|_{\text{hor}}$), and (e-f) local ($\mathcal{T}|_{\text{hor}}$), following (12). Positive and negative values correspond to variance transfers from ETV to MTV and from MTV to ETV, respectively. Contours show Conservative temperature with contours from -2°C to 13°C with 1.5° contour interval.

TABLE 2: Spatial-averages of the horizontal variance transfers, following (12), both at global and regional level. The 6 regions (Fig. 9) corresponds to: the whole North Atlantic (80°W-0° and 25°N-60°N), the Western North Atlantic (80°W-46°W and 25°N-60°N), the Central North Atlantic (46°W-30°W and 25°N-60°N), the Eastern North Atlantic (30°W-0° and 25°N-60°N), the Agulhas Current sector (10°E-90°E and 55°S-20°S) and the Southern Ocean sector (south of 35°S). Positive and negative values correspond to variance transfers from ETV to MTV and from MTV to ETV, respectively. The residual reflects the error of the diagnostics.

$(10^{-9} \text{ K}^2 \text{ s}^{-1})$	Global	North Atlantic			Agulhas	Southern	
	Mean	All	West	Central	East	Current	Ocean
Total	-0.5	-5.6	3.7	-5.5	-14.9	-0.4	-1.7
Non-Local	0.2	0.2	1.9	-0.2	-1.1	1.4	-0.8
Local	-0.7	-6.0	1.8	-5.2	-14.3	-1.5	-0.8
Residual	0.0	0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.5	-0.3	-0.1

441 *c. Consequences for mean-temperature distribution maintenance*

442 Since \mathcal{T} is the only term that has a global impact and hence any impact on the width of the
443 mean temperature distribution, we focus on this term in the following subsection.

444 We decompose the global variance transfer in term of temperature classes to determine
445 how each class contributes to the overall shrinking of the mean temperature distribution.
446 Following Water Mass transformations framework (Walín, 1982), one can derive the variance
447 transformations as a function of temperature classes. This reads:

$$\Psi^\# = \rho_0 C_p \partial_{\bar{T}} \iint_{S(\bar{\Theta}'' \leq \bar{\Theta})} \mathcal{T} ds \Delta z, \quad (17)$$

448 where $S(\bar{\Theta}'' \leq \bar{\Theta})$ is ocean surface at 1 000 m with temperature lower than or equal to $\bar{\Theta}$, ρ_0
449 is the reference density, C_p is the ocean heat capacity, and Δz is an ocean layer thickness. As
450 discussed in Sévellec et al. (2025b), Δz should be set based on the increment of the temper-
451 ature classes to make $\Psi^\#$ independent of this increment choice. At this depth, Sévellec et al.
452 (2025b) suggest the use of $\Delta z|_{\text{ref}}=70$ m for a neutral density increment of $\Delta\gamma|_{\text{ref}}=0.03 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$.
453 Hence, through a scaling, this corresponds to a thickness $\Delta z=\alpha\Delta T\Delta z|_{\text{ref}}/\Delta\gamma|_{\text{ref}}=58.3$ m for
454 our temperature increment of $\Delta T=0.25$ K (and a spatial-mean thermal expansion coefficient
455 of $\alpha=0.1 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$).

456 This diagnostic reveals that for almost all the temperature classes the variance transfers
457 contributes to the shrinking of mean temperature distribution (Fig. 10). This remarkable
458 consistency contrasts with the intricate structure of the geographical distribution of the vari-
459 ance transfers (Fig. 8c). For a few water classes, however, the variance transfers lead to a

460 broadening of the distribution. This is the case for extreme water classes: Conservative Tem-
 461 perature below 0.5°C and above 11.25°C . (Although this result has to be moderated since
 462 these temperature ranges correspond to poleward locations where there is the least amount
 463 of observations.) It is also the case for Conservative Temperature between 6.5°C and 7.25°C .
 464 Overall, the variance transformation is not proportional to the volume of water, for instance
 465 the AAIW has the largest volume, but this is not where the variance transformation maxi-
 466 mum occurs. Basically the volume-distribution is sharper than the variance-transformations.
 467 Also there is a temperature-class lag of their distribution center with a peak at $\sim 4.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and
 468 between 5°C and 5.5°C for the former and the latter, respectively.

FIGURE 10: As Fig. 8c but as a distribution in terms of conservative temperature classes, following (17). This corresponds to the distribution of local eddy-mean interactions for the temperature variance ($\mathcal{T}|_{\text{hor}}$), following (12), as a function of the mean temperature. Positive (orange) and negative (cyan) values correspond to variance transfers from ETV to MTV and from MTV to ETV, respectively. The relative volume of each water class is given by the grey patch. Temperature classes are spaced by 0.25°C and the volume curves have been smoothed using a 1°C moving average. The horizontal color patches show properties of selected Water Masses: AntArctic Bottom Water (AABW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), AntArctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), Red Sea-Persian Gulf Intermediate Intermediate Water (RSPGIW), Mediterranean Water (MW), North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW), and the Arctic Intermediate Water (AIW), following Emery (2018). These water mass locations are depicted in the inset.

469 To describe the variance transformations as a function of Water Masses, we first defined

470 7 main Water Masses located at 1 000-m depth. These correspond to the Arctic Interme-
471 diate Water (AIW: $-1.50-3.00^\circ\text{C}$ and $34.87-35.17 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$), the AntArctic Bottom Water
472 (AABW: $-0.90-1.70^\circ\text{C}$ and $34.81-34.89 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$), the Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW: $0.10-$
473 2.00°C and $34.78-34.90 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$), the North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW: $1.50-4.00^\circ\text{C}$ and
474 $34.97-35.17 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$), the AntArctic Intermediate Water (AAIW: $2.01-10.00^\circ\text{C}$ and $33.96-$
475 34.97 g kg^{-1}), the Mediterranean Water (MW: $2.60-10.97^\circ\text{C}$ and $35.17-36.38 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$), and the
476 Red Sea–Persian Gulf Intermediate Intermediate Water (RSPGIW: $5.00-13.98^\circ\text{C}$ and $34.97-$
477 35.57 g kg^{-1}). The above Conservative Temperature and Absolute Salinity characteristics
478 have been derived from Emery (2018) and positioned using both Conservative Temperature
479 and Absolute Salinity from ISAS17 (inset of Fig. 10). This description allows for charac-
480 terizing for water masses with a positive variance transformation: the AIW, the AABW,
481 the RSPGIW and the mildest part of the MW (Fig. 10). On the other hand, the other
482 Water Masses all correspond to an overall negative variance transfer of mean temperature
483 variance. This sharpening of the temperature distribution is particularly active within the
484 MW (Fig. 10).

485 *d. Implications for mean-temperature structure balance*

486 Moving back to the global-mean temperature variance transfers, at high Péclet number and
487 at equilibrium ($\partial_t \bar{T}^2=0$), from (10) we have $2 \langle \bar{T} \bar{F} \rangle = - \langle \mathcal{T} \rangle$. Assuming an optimal flux (i.e.,
488 perfect match with the temperature structure), we have $\bar{F}_{\text{opt}} = \phi \frac{\bar{T}}{\sigma_T}$ (where ϕ is a scalar)
489 and we obtain: $\phi = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\langle \mathcal{T} \rangle}{\sigma_T}$. Applying it to our horizontal framework, the minimum heat flux
490 amplitude to balance the transfer terms is $\phi|_{\text{hor}}=2.0 \times 10^{-10} \text{ K s}^{-1}$ or $4.7 \times 10^{-2} \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (after
491 multiplying by $\rho_o C_p \Delta z$ to obtain an equivalent heat flux). This suggests that the minimal
492 heat flux to maintain the horizontal temperature structure at 1 000 m given the action of
493 the turbulence corresponds to a warming of $\sim 1 \text{ K}$ per 150 years.

494 Since this study focuses only on the horizontal component, the reference conservative
495 temperature is a horizontal average (i.e., $\langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}}$). Hence a pseudo-vertical advection of the
496 form $\bar{w} \partial_z \langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}}$ was incorporated to the mean-temperature evolution equation as a forcing
497 term, as explained in section 3a.. At 1 000-m depth, this should be the main/key term in the
498 forcing term (i.e., $\bar{F}|_{\text{hor}}$). This allows for the computation of an optimal vertical velocity,
499 following $\bar{F}_{\text{opt}}|_{\text{hor}} = -\bar{w}_{\text{opt}} \partial_z \langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}}$ and using the expression of \bar{F}_{opt} provided above. This
500 reads:

$$\bar{w}_{\text{opt}} = \frac{\bar{T}}{2 \partial_z \langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}}} \frac{\langle \mathcal{T}|_{\text{hor}} \rangle_{\text{hor}}}{\sigma_T^2|_{\text{hor}}}, \quad (18)$$

501 where $\sigma_T^2|_{\text{hor}} = \langle \bar{T}^2 \rangle_{\text{hor}}$ is the horizontal variance of the mean temperature. This corresponds
502 to a transfer from the reference state ($\langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}}$) to the mean temperature structure (\bar{T}^2) by
503 mean vertical motions (\bar{w}). This is equivalent to a transfer between the Background Potential

504 Energy and the Available Potential Energy, in the context of potential energy transfers.
505 (Note that, even at equilibrium, the equality linking variance transfers and forcing is only
506 true on global average, since locally advection can transport from local sources to local
507 sinks.) Since the ANDRO database does not contain observations of vertical temperature
508 shear, we computed it from the ISAS product (Kolodziejczyk et al., 2023). We find values
509 of \bar{w}_{opt} of the order of 10^{-7} m s^{-1} (Fig. 11), which corresponds to about a centimeter per
510 day. This values is weaker and so consistent with mesoscale vertical velocity estimations of
511 Christensen et al. (2004). As expected from the formulation of (18), the horizontal structure
512 varies together with the mean temperature. This leads to upwelling of the colder waters:
513 AABW, CDW, NADW, and AIW; and downwelling of MW and RSPGIW (as well as of its
514 residual within the recirculation of the Agulhas Current); the AAIW is both upwelled and
515 downwelled depending if it is below or above a conservative temperature of $\langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}} \simeq 4.36^\circ\text{C}$
516 (this threshold is an obvious consequence of the definition of $T = \Theta - \langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}}$). Maximum
517 upwelling occurs in the Nordic Seas, whereas downwelling occurs off the Portugal coast.

FIGURE 11: Optimal equivalent vertical velocity, following (18). This vertical velocity leads to the most efficient mean vertical advection allowing for a global compensation of the variance transfer (\mathcal{T}). (Note that, even at equilibrium, there is no need for a perfect local compensation, since advection can transport variance from local sources to local sinks.) Grey contour shows Conservative Temperature of $\langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}} \simeq 4.36^\circ\text{C}$ and perfectly matches $\bar{w}_{\text{opt}} = 0$ by construction of the anomalous Conservative Temperature (i.e., $T = \Theta - \langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}}$).

518 Comparison with actual vertical velocity at 1 000-m depth (w_{real}) should be done carefully.

519 Indeed the optimal vertical velocity is the minimum vertical velocity needed to balance the
520 temperature variance transfers, so it does not have to exactly reflect the real velocity. Hence,
521 the actual vertical velocity only needs to contain the optimal velocity for consistency. Liang
522 et al. (2017) and Cortés-Morales and Lazar (2024) have provided estimations of the vertical
523 velocity, and in particular at 1 000-m depth. It corresponds to a flow of a few to several
524 10^{-6} m s⁻¹. This is, at least, one order of magnitude above the required optimal velocity.
525 At this depth the retrieved estimated vertical velocity pattern bears a resemblance to the
526 Ekman (1905) pumping pattern (Marshall and Plumb, 2007; Wunsch, 2011; Roquet et al.,
527 2011). Hence w_{real} corresponds to upwelling in the subpolar regions and a downwelling in the
528 poleward part of subtropical regions (north of 30°N and south of 30°S for the northern and
529 southern hemisphere, respectively). This is overall quite consistent with our optimal vertical
530 velocity (Fig. 11). In particular, positive values in the subpolar North Atlantic and North
531 Pacific, positive values in Southern Ocean, negative values along the North Atlantic Current
532 and within the Mediterranean Water, and negative values within the Agulhas current, its
533 retroflection, and its merging with the ACC are all consistent signatures of both w_{real} and
534 w_{opt} . This suggests the positive projection of w_{opt} onto w_{real} and that w_{opt} can be indeed
535 contained within w_{real} . Hence, even if not a perfect validation of w_{opt} , we can conclude
536 that independent estimations of w_{real} are consistent with our framework and results. This
537 suggests that the observed mean upwelling has the potential to balance the variance transfers
538 estimated in the present study.

539 5 Discussions

540 In this study, we have developed a consistent framework to track and assess the eddy-mean
541 interactions of temperature variance. To this purpose we have built on analyses of variance
542 budget (e.g., Sévellec et al., 2006; Buckley et al., 2012; Sévellec et al., 2021) and of Kinetic
543 Energy interactions (e.g., Chen et al., 2014, 2016; Sévellec et al., 2025a) to disentangle the
544 temperature variance exchanges between the mean and the turbulence. This framework has
545 some analogy with studies looking at potential energy exchanges (e.g., Kang and Curchitser,
546 2015; Chen et al., 2016; Jamet et al., 2024). We find that the eddy-mean interactions are well
547 described using three reservoirs: the Mean Temperature Variance, the Residual Temperature
548 Variance, and the Eddy Temperature Variance (Fig. 3). They correspond to the zeroth, first,
549 and second order terms of the temperature square, respectively. The RTV is peculiar in the
550 sense that it is zero on average, but it is key in the sense that it acts as a mediator between
551 MTV and ETV. In this context, we have shown that the total interactions are the sum of
552 the non-local and local interactions, where the former corresponds to a temperature variance
553 redistribution and the latter corresponds to the temperature variance transfers.

554 To compute the temperature variance interactions we have used consistent, *in situ* global

555 observations of temperature and horizontal velocity provided by the ANDRO dataset (Olli-
556 trault and Rannou, 2013). The ANDRO dataset is based on deep Argo float displacements,
557 limiting our study to 1 000-m depth. We find that the across-isothermal turbulent temper-
558 ature fluxes are only 55% downgradient, challenging the applicability of downgradient flux
559 closure (Redi, 1982) to accurately represent temperature variance transfers. Regarding the
560 temperature variance interactions, the pattern shows intensification in the Gulf Stream, in
561 the North Atlantic Current, in the Agulhas retroflection, and in both ACC of the Indian
562 Ocean sector and of the Pacific Ocean sector. The typical length scale signature varies from
563 several degrees to around a dozen of degrees. At the scale of the computation (i.e., $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$),
564 the non-local terms are more intense than the local terms, leading to their dominance on the
565 total interactions.

566 When averaged over larger area, in almost all tested regions and in the global average the
567 variance transfers (i.e., local term $-\mathcal{T}$) is negative and is the dominant term for the eddy-
568 mean interactions (i.e., total term $-\mathcal{R}$). This suggests a shrinking of the mean temperature
569 distribution (restoring toward the mean value, consistently with the intuitive description of
570 Zika et al., 2012) and an intensification of turbulent activity. This view is also correct when
571 looking at average effect over mean temperature classes, where most of them correspond
572 to a shrinking of the mean temperature distribution. This suggests that, unlike for the
573 $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ -scale, the downgradient flux closure can represent accurately water mass variance
574 transformation. In contrast, the western North Atlantic is the only tested region where the
575 turbulence acts to broaden the mean temperature distribution, whereas turbulent activity is
576 damped. Hence this region acts as a graveyard for turbulence allowing the maintenance of
577 mean-temperature structure, hence of the mean-circulation. Extrapolating this result to the
578 full water column, this is consistent with this particular region being a warm region ($\bar{T} > 0$)
579 where the ocean releases heat to the atmosphere ($\bar{F} < 0$, Tomita et al., 2021, for instance),
580 and so having a negative correlation between heat flux and anomalous temperature field
581 ($\bar{T}\bar{F} < 0$). This leads to a mean temperature damping effect by the heat flux ($\partial_t \bar{T}^2 < 0$),
582 which needs to be maintained by turbulent processes ($\mathcal{T} > 0$). This is also supported by the
583 relatively important positive contribution of the variance redistribution (i.e., nonlocal term
584 $-\mathcal{A}$) which also compensates the action of the heat flux and contributes to the maintenance
585 the mean temperature structure of this region.

586 Even if our study is only centered around the 1 000-m depth, the properties of the in-
587 teractions give us a unique observational insight on the dynamics of the ocean. Indeed,
588 generalizing our results that the global-mean variance transfers are negative ($\langle \mathcal{T} \rangle < 0$) has
589 implication for the ocean equilibrium. To this purpose we first need to acknowledge a few
590 properties: the large-scale dissipation term is negligible (i.e., high Péclet number: $\langle \bar{T}\bar{D} \rangle \simeq 0$),
591 the small-scale dissipation is of leading order and negative (as demonstrated in this study:

592 $\langle \overline{T'D'} \rangle \leq 0$), the large-scale forcing is positive (i.e., warming in warm areas and cooling in
 593 cold areas: $\langle \overline{T\bar{F}} \rangle > 0$), and we can hypothesize that the small-scale forcing, if it exists, is
 594 negative (i.e., warm and cold eddies transfer their properties to the atmosphere: $\langle \overline{T'F'} \rangle \leq 0$).
 595 This leads to the conclusion that, at equilibrium and globally, the mean large-scale forcing
 596 is either re-injected to the atmosphere as small-scale forcing or is transferred toward turbu-
 597 lent small-scale ocean dissipation: $\xrightarrow{2\langle \overline{T\bar{F}} \rangle} \sigma_T^2 \xrightarrow{\mathcal{T}} \langle \sigma_{T'}^2 \rangle \xrightarrow{2\langle \overline{T'F'} \rangle} \frac{2\langle \overline{T'F'} \rangle}{2\langle \overline{T'D'} \rangle}$. This is a (partial) observational
 598 evidence of the direct cascade of temperature variance, already established in an idealized-
 599 configuration modeling study (Hochet et al., 2020), similar to the expected direct cascade of
 600 potential energy (Rhines, 1977; Salmon, 1978, 1980). This means that the large-scale forc-
 601 ing broadens the large-scale distribution which is balanced by a shrinking effect of variance
 602 transfers toward small-scale variance, this small-scale variance increases being balanced by
 603 small-scale dissipation or possibly a net anti-correlation of small-scale forcing and small-scale
 604 temperature anomaly. Hence our study opens the possibility of rationalizing the ocean as
 605 a “device” converting large-scale forcing from the atmosphere to small-scale forcing to the
 606 atmosphere (Small et al., 2008) with some efficiency (i.e., small-scale ocean dissipation).
 607 Determining the relative effect of small-scale forcing and small-scale dissipation will be the
 608 goal of future analyses.

609 One consequence of our framework consistently with our limited dataset (i.e., a single slice
 610 of the ocean at 1 000-m depth) is the need to define a background mean temperature gradient
 611 ($\partial_z \langle \Theta \rangle$). This background provides a source of variance through vertical motion impacting
 612 the mean temperature variance. This has allowed us to estimate an optimal vertical velocity
 613 needed to compensate the transfers toward the eddy variance, which corresponds to only a
 614 few centimeter per day. Whereas the Abyssal Recipes allows for an estimation of the required
 615 turbulence based on observed circulation (Munk and Wunsch, 1998), here we have used
 616 turbulence observations to estimate the required vertical velocity. This background ($\langle \Theta \rangle_{\text{hor}}$)
 617 bears obvious resemblance with the reference state used to define the Background Potential
 618 Energy (Lorenz, 1955; Hochet et al., 2022), whereas the MTV and ETV (\bar{T}^2 and T'^2) are
 619 analog to the mean- and eddy- Available Potential Energy (Lorenz, 1955; Hochet et al.,
 620 2022), respectively. Building on this relation might help define the background temperature,
 621 central to our study, in a robust, physically-meaningful, and elegant manner.

622 Our study being at a single depth, it obviously suffers from a limited view. Building a
 623 full three-dimensional picture based on observations of the eddy-mean interactions of tem-
 624 perature, salinity, and density variance will be the goal of future investigations. Beyond
 625 observations, testing our framework and results in long climate simulations which include
 626 eddy-resolving ocean models is a direction for future work. Indeed our study provides an
 627 observational estimate that can help test and validate eddy-resolving ocean numerical sim-
 628 ulations. It also provides a step forward for further developments and implementations of

629 ocean turbulent closures for laminar ocean numerical models.

630 **Appendix: physical interpretation of the eddy-mean interactions**

631 In this appendix, we derived the turbulent heat flux as well as the total, local, and non-local
 632 interactions following two classical frameworks. This provides physical interpretations of the
 633 eddy-mean interaction terms.

634 *Rotational and divergent decomposition*

635 Following the Helmholtz decomposition, Marshall and Shutts (1981) and Fox-Kemper et al.
 636 (2003) suggested that the turbulent heat flux can be decomposed into a divergent and a
 637 rotational component. This reads:

$$\overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}|_{\text{div}} = \nabla \phi, \quad (\text{A1a})$$

638

$$\overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}|_{\text{rot}} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}, \quad (\text{A1b})$$

639 where ϕ is a scalar potential and \mathbf{A} is a vector potential. (Note that ϕ and \mathbf{A} are not uniquely
 640 defined, Fox-Kemper et al., 2003, leading, in practice, to the indeterminacy decomposition.)
 641 This framework leads a simplification of the flux divergence acting on the mean-temperature,
 642 as indicated in (6a):

$$\nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}|_{\text{div}} = \nabla^2 \phi, \quad (\text{A2a})$$

643

$$\nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}|_{\text{rot}} = 0, \quad (\text{A2b})$$

644 where ∇^2 is the Laplacian ($=\nabla^\dagger \cdot \nabla = \partial_x^2 + \partial_y^2 + \partial_z^2$). This implies that only the divergent term
 645 is important for the mean-temperature evolution (Marshall and Shutts, 1981). (A2) is now
 646 routinely applied in oceanographic studies (e.g., Aoki et al., 2013; Guo and Bishop, 2022).
 647 It potentially solves the apparent paradox of the important (45%) upgradient turbulent heat
 648 fluxes: part of them can come from the rotational term.

649 For the variance transfers [i.e., local interactions: $\mathcal{T}=2(\nabla\bar{T})^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}$], both divergent and
 650 rotational components are potentially important. However we have:

$$(\nabla\bar{T})^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}|_{\text{rot}} = \nabla^\dagger \cdot (\bar{T} \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}|_{\text{rot}}). \quad (\text{A3})$$

651 Hence, assuming no net variance flux at the boundaries, we know that:

$$\iiint_V (\nabla\bar{T})^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}|_{\text{rot}} dv = 0. \quad (\text{A4})$$

652 This means that the rotational component does not contribute to a net global temperature
 653 variance transfer.

654 We can conclude that, at the computational scale, both divergent and rotational compo-
655 nents will be at play for the transfers and that the upgradient and downgradient properties of
656 the turbulent heat flux select the direction of the transfers (i.e., toward the mean and toward
657 the eddy, respectively). However at global-scale only the divergent component contributes.
658 We hypothesize that there exists a spatial-scale over which the rotational component of the
659 transfers vanishes. Under this assumption, a downgradient closure of the divergent compo-
660 nent is consistent with our observations of negative transfers at global-scale and for most
661 tested spatial and Water Mass averages (Tab. 2 and Fig.10). Whereas this downgradient
662 closure would be valid at all-scale for the mean-temperature evolution, it would only be valid
663 over this hypothesized spatial-scale for variance transfers.

664 *Symmetric and antisymmetric decomposition*

665 Here we follow an other classical theoretical framework, namely the Temporal-Residual-Mean
666 (McDougall and McIntosh, 2001). This framework shows that the turbulent temperature flux
667 can be represented through the mean temperature gradient. This reads:

$$\overline{\mathbf{u}'T'} \sim -(\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{S}) \cdot \nabla \bar{T}, \quad (\text{A5})$$

668 where \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{S} are antisymmetric and symmetric tensors, respectively. They represent
669 rotation and deformation associated to eddy advection and diffusion closure, respectively.

670 Applying it to the total, local, and non-local interaction terms, following (7), we have:

$$\mathcal{R} = -2\bar{T}\nabla^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'} \sim \nabla^\dagger \cdot [(\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{S}) \cdot \nabla \bar{T}^2] - 2(\nabla \bar{T})^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot \nabla \bar{T}, \quad (\text{A6a})$$

$$\mathcal{A} = -2\nabla^\dagger \cdot (\bar{T}\overline{\mathbf{u}'T'}) \sim \nabla^\dagger \cdot [(\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{S}) \cdot \nabla \bar{T}^2], \quad (\text{A6b})$$

$$\mathcal{T} = 2(\nabla \bar{T})^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}'T'} \sim -2(\nabla \bar{T})^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot \nabla \bar{T}, \quad (\text{A6c})$$

673 These formulation help us reinterpret the local and non-local terms. The non-local term cor-
674 responds to the eddy-advection and eddy-diffusion of mean temperature variance (exhibiting
675 the action of both antisymmetric and symmetric tensor). They correspond to a spatial-
676 redistribution of variance (i.e., conserving the global mean-variance). With this formulation,
677 the residual temperature variance appears less useful as the mean temperature variance
678 is self-consistent (as expected for the Temporal-Residual-Mean framework, McDougall and
679 McIntosh, 2001). At the opposite, the local term is only controlled by the symmetric tensor.
680 Also its global integral does not vanish. This implies the possibility of a net global variance
681 transfer between mean and eddy temperature variance. Consequently and as mentioned in
682 McDougall and McIntosh (2001) for density, only the symmetric component acts on the eddy
683 temperature variance.

684 To further characterize the physical constraint behind the local term, we can split the
 685 symmetric tensor through an eigen-decomposition. The local term becomes:

$$(\nabla\bar{T})^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot \nabla\bar{T} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \kappa_i \left(\mathbf{s}_i^\dagger \cdot \nabla\bar{T} \right)^2, \quad (\text{A7})$$

686 where κ_i are the three diffusivity coefficients along the three natural direction \mathbf{s}_i , such as
 687 $\mathbf{S} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \kappa_i \mathbf{s}_i \cdot \mathbf{s}_i^\dagger$ (i.e., an eigen-decomposition of \mathbf{S}). Hence $\mathcal{T} > 0$ can only come from a
 688 negative diffusivity coefficient (κ_i), reminiscent of the negative viscosity of Starr (1968).

689 This formulation suggests that, beyond the existence of rotational fluxes, the existence
 690 of $\mathcal{T} > 0$ (Fig. 8c) is inconsistent with the Fick’s law closure. Only when averaged over
 691 large spatial-scale or water masses this downgradient flux closure appears consistent with
 692 our observations (Tab. 2 and Fig. 10, respectively), except for a few peculiar regions or
 693 water classes. It is worth noting that state-of-the-art direct and indirect estimations often
 694 lead, sometimes by construction, to positive definite diffusivity coefficients (e.g., Klocker and
 695 Abernathey, 2014; Groeskamp et al., 2020; Roach et al., 2018; Sévellec et al., 2022). This
 696 has the inherent consequence of restricting variance transfers from the mean to the eddy.

697

698 *Acknowledgment.* This work was supported by ARVOR, OASIS, and VACARM projects
 699 from LEFE IMAGO and GMMC programs, and by the OceaniX project funded through
 700 the French ANR program, and by the ISblue project, Interdisciplinary graduate school
 701 for the blue planet (ANR-17-EURE-0015) co-funded by a grant from the French govern-
 702 ment under the program “Investissements d’Avenir”. ANDRO Argo floats displacements
 703 product is made freely available by SNO Argo France at LOPS Laboratory (supported by
 704 UBO/CNRS/Ifremer/IRD) and IUEM Observatory (OSU IUEM/CNRS/INSU), and was
 705 funded by Ifremer, Coriolis, SOERE-CTDO2, SNO Argo France, and CPER region Bre-
 706 tagne OBSOCEAN. Florian Sévellec, Antoine Hochet, and Thierry Huck are supported by
 707 the EERIE project (Grant Agreement No 101081383) funded by the European Union. Views
 708 and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect
 709 those of the European Union or the European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Ex-
 710 ecutive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be
 711 held responsible for them.

712

713 *Data Availability.* The ANDRO dataset used in this study corresponds to the 2025 Release
 714 (key: ‘116520’) and is available at <https://doi.org/10.17882/47077>. The ISAS17 dataset
 715 provides a global three-dimensional gridded temperature and salinity data derived from

716 objective analysis of in situ observations and is available at <https://doi.org/10.17882/>
717 52367.

718 **References**

- 719 Aoki, K., S. Minobe, Y. Tanimoto, and Y. Sasai, 2013: Southward eddy heat transport
720 occurring along southern flanks of the kuroshio extension and the gulf stream in a 1/108
721 global ocean general circulation model. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **43**, 1899–1910.
- 722 Arzel, O., T. Huck, and A. Colin de Verdière, 2006: The different nature of the interdecadal
723 variability of the thermohaline circulation under mixed and flux boundary conditions. *J.*
724 *Phys. Oceanogr.*, **36**, 1703–1718.
- 725 Batchelor, G. K., 1949: Diffusion in a field of homogeneous turbulence. *Australian Journal*
726 *of Scientific Research*, **2**, 437–450.
- 727 Bretherton, F. P., R. Davis, and C. Fandry, 1976: Technique for objective analysis and design
728 of oceanographic experiment applied to MODE-73. *Deep-Sea Res. Oceanogr. Abstr.*, **23**,
729 559–582.
- 730 Buckley, M. W., D. Ferreira, J.-M. Campin, J. Marshall, and R. Tulloch, 2012: On the
731 relationship between decadal buoyancy anomalies and variability of the atlantic meridional
732 overturning circulation. *J. Climate*, **25**, 8009–8030.
- 733 Charney, J., 1947: The dynamics of long waves in a baroclinic westerly current. *J. Meteor.*,
734 **4**, 135–162.
- 735 Chelton, D. B., M. G. Schlax, S. R. M. and R. A. deSzoeki, 2007: Global observations of
736 large oceanic eddies. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, **34**, L15 606.
- 737 Chen, R., G. R. Flierl, and C. Wunsch, 2014: A description of local and nonlocal eddy-
738 mean flow interaction in a global eddy-permitting state estimate. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **44**,
739 2336–2352.
- 740 Chen, R., A. F. Thompson, and G. R. Flierl, 2016: Time-dependent eddy-mean energy
741 diagrams and their application to the ocean. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **46**, 2827–2850.
- 742 Christensen, K., A. R. Gray, and S. C. Riser, 2004: Global estimates of mesoscale ver-
743 tical velocity near 1,000 m from argo observations. *J. Geophys. Res.: Oceans*, **129**,
744 e2023JC020 003.
- 745 Colin de Verdière, A., and R. Tailleux, 2005: The interaction of a baroclinic mean flow with
746 long rossby waves. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **35**, 865–879.
- 747 Cortés-Morales, D., and A. Lazar, 2024: Vertical velocity 3D estimates from the linear
748 vorticity balance in the North Atlantic ocean. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **54**, 2185–2203.

- 749 Eady, E. T., 1949: Long waves and cyclone waves. *Tellus*, **1**, 33–52.
- 750 Ekman, V. W., 1905: On the influence of the earth’s rotation on ocean currents. *Ark. Mat.*
751 *Astron. Fys.*, **2**, 1–52.
- 752 Emery, W. J., 2018: Ocean circulation — Water Types and Water Masses. *Encyclopedia of*
753 *Atmospheric Sciences*, J. R. Holton, Ed., Academic Press, Oxford, 1556–1567.
- 754 Ferrari, R., and C. Wunsch, 2009: Ocean circulation Kinetic Energy: Reservoirs, sources,
755 and sinks. *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.*, **41**, 253–282.
- 756 Fox-Kemper, B., R. Ferrari, and J. Pedlosky, 2003: On the indeterminacy of rotational and
757 divergent eddy fluxes. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **33**, 478–483.
- 758 Gaillard, F., T. Reynaud, V. Thierry, N. Kolodziejczyk, and K. von Schuckmann, 2016: In-
759 situ based reanalysis of the global ocean temperature and salinity with ISAS: variability
760 of the heat content and steric height. *J. Climate*, **29**, 1305–1323.
- 761 Groeskamp, S., J. H. LaCasce, T. J. McDougall, and M. Rogé, 2020: Full-depth global
762 estimates of ocean mesoscale eddy mixing from observations and theory. *Geophys. Res.*
763 *Lett.*, **47**, e2020GL089425.
- 764 Guo, Y., and S. P. Bishop, 2022: Surface divergent eddy heat fluxes and their impacts on
765 mixed layer eddy-mean flow interaction. *J. Adv. Model. Earth Syst.*, **14**, 805–807.
- 766 Hochet, A., T. Huck, O. Arzel, F. Sévellec, and A. Colin de Verdière, 2022: Energy transfers
767 between multidecadal and turbulent variability. *J. Climate*, **35**, 1157–1178.
- 768 Hochet, A., T. Huck, O. Arzel, F. Sévellec, M. Mazloff, B. Cornuelle, and A. Colin de
769 Verdière, 2020: Direct temporal cascade of temperature variance in eddy-permitting sim-
770 ulations of multidecadal variability. *J. Climate*, **33**, 9409–9425.
- 771 Hochet, A., C. Lique, F. Sévellec, and W. Llovel, 2024a: Drivers of interannual salinity
772 variability in the arctic ocean. *J. Geophys. Res.: Oceans*, **29**, e2023JC020852.
- 773 Hochet, A., W. Llovel, T. Huck, and F. Sévellec, 2024b: Advection-surface flux balance
774 controls the seasonal steric sea level amplitude. *Sci. Rep.*, **14**, 10644.
- 775 Hochet, A., W. Llovel, F. Sévellec, and T. Huck, 2023: Sources and sinks of interannual
776 steric sea level variability. *J. Geophys. Res.: Oceans*, **128**, e2022JC019335.
- 777 Hochet, A., F. Sévellec, and N. Kolodziejczyk, 2026: The role of large-scale seasonal cycle
778 advection in maintaining the mean ocean salinity distribution. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, **53**,
779 e2025GL119040.

- 780 Holland, W. R., 1978: The role of mesoscale eddies in the general circulation of the ocean–
781 numerical experiments using a wind-driven quasi-geostrophic model. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*,
782 **8**, 363–392.
- 783 IPCC, 2021: *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Work-*
784 *ing Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate*
785 *Change*. Cambridge University Press.
- 786 Jamet, Q., A. Berger, B. Deremble, and T. Penduff, 2024: Thermodynamical effects of ocean
787 current feedback in a quasigeostrophic coupled model. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **54**, 1691–1704.
- 788 Jamet, Q., S. Leroux, W. K. Dewar, T. Penduff, J. Le Sommer, J.-M. Molines, and J. Gula,
789 2022: Non-local eddy-mean kinetic energy transfers in submesoscale-permitting ensemble
790 simulations. *J. Adv. Model. Earth Syst.*, **14**, e2022MS003057.
- 791 Kang, D., and E. N. Curchitser, 2015: Energetics of eddy-mean flow interactions in the Gulf
792 Stream region. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **45**, 1103–1120.
- 793 Klocker, A., and R. Abernathey, 2014: Global patterns of mesoscale eddy properties and
794 diffusivities. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **44**, 1030–1046.
- 795 Kolodziejczyk, N., A. Prigent-Mazella, and F. Gaillard, 2023: ISAS temperature, salinity,
796 dissolved oxygen gridded fields. *SEANOE*, <https://doi.org/10.17882/52367>.
- 797 Liang, X., M. Spall, and C. Wunsch, 2017: Global ocean vertical velocity from
798 a dynamically consistent ocean state estimate. *J. Geophys. Res.: Oceans*, **122**,
799 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JC012985>.
- 800 Lorenz, E. N., 1955: Available Potential Energy and the maintenance of the general circu-
801 lation. *Tellus*, **VII**, 2, 157–167.
- 802 Marshall, J., and R. A. Plumb, 2007: *Atmosphere, Ocean and Climate Dynamics: An In-*
803 *troductory Text*. Academic Press, 344pp pp.
- 804 Marshall, J., and G. Shutts, 1981: A note on rotational and divergent eddy fluxes. *J. Phys.*
805 *Oceanogr.*, **11**, 1677–1680.
- 806 Matsuta, T., and Y. Masumoto, 2021: Modified view of energy budget diagram and its
807 application to the Kuroshio extension region. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **51**, 1163–1175.
- 808 McDougall, T. J., and P. M. Barker, 2011: Getting started with teos-10 and the gibbs
809 seawater (gsw) oceanographic toolbox. Tech. rep., SCOR/IAPSO WG127, 28pp pp.

- 810 McDougall, T. J., S. Groeskamp, and S. M. Griffies, 2014: On geometrical aspects of interior
811 ocean mixing. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **44**, 2164–2175.
- 812 McDougall, T. J., and P. C. McIntosh, 2001: The Temporal-Residual-Mean velocity. part II:
813 Isopycnal interpretation and the tracer and momentum equations. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **31**,
814 1222–1246.
- 815 Munk, W., and C. Wunsch, 1998: Abyssal recipes II : Energetics of tidal and wind mixing.
816 *Deep-Sea Res. Part I*, **45**, 1977–2010.
- 817 Murakami, S., 2011: Atmospheric local energetics and energy interactions between mean
818 and eddy fields. Part I: Theory. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **68**, 760–768.
- 819 Murakami, S., R. Ohgaito, and A. Abe-Ouchi, 2011: Atmospheric local energetics and en-
820 ergy interactions between mean and eddy fields. Part II: An example for the last glacial
821 maximum climate. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **68**, 533–552.
- 822 Ollitrault, M., and J. P. Rannou, 2013: An Argo-based deep displacement dataset. *J. Atmos.*
823 *Oceanic Technol.*, **30**, 759–788.
- 824 Ollitrault, M., P. Rannou, E. Brion, C. Cabanes, A. Piron, G. Reverdin, and
825 N. Kolodziejczyk, 2025: ANDRO: An Argo-based deep displacement dataset. *SEANOE*,
826 <https://doi.org/10.17882/47077>.
- 827 Redi, M. H., 1982: Oceanic isopycnal mixing by coordinate rotation. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*,
828 **12**, 1154–1158.
- 829 Rhines, P. B., 1977: The dynamics of unsteady currents. *The Sea*, **Vol. VI**, John Wiley and
830 Sons, New York.
- 831 Rhines, P. B., and W. R. Holland, 1979: A theoretical discussion of eddy-driven mean flows.
832 *Dyn. Atmos. and Oceans*, **3**, 289–325.
- 833 Roach, C. J., D. Bawada, and K. Speer, 2018: Global observations of horizontal mix-
834 ing from Argo float and surface drifter trajectories. *J. Geophys. Res.: Oceans*, **123**,
835 doi:10.1029/2018JC013750.
- 836 Roquet, F., C. Wunsch, and G. Madec, 2011: On the patterns of wind-power input to the
837 ocean circulation. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **41**, 2328–2342.
- 838 Salmon, R. B., 1978: Two-layer quasi-geostrophic turbulence in a simple special case. *Geo-*
839 *phys. Astrophys. Fluid Dyn.*, **10**, 25–52.

- 840 Salmon, R. B., 1980: Baroclinic instability and geostrophic turbulence. *Geophys. Astrophys.*
841 *Fluid Dyn.*, **10**, 167–211.
- 842 Sévellec, F., A. Colin de Verdière, and N. Kolodziejczyk, 2022: Estimation of horizontal
843 turbulent diffusivity from deep Argo float displacements. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **52**, 1509–
844 1529.
- 845 Sévellec, F., A. Colin de Verdière, and N. Kolodziejczyk, 2024: Global observations of deep
846 ocean kinetic energy transfers. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **54**, 1633–1654.
- 847 Sévellec, F., and T. Huck, 2015: Theoretical investigation of the atlantic multidecadal oscil-
848 lation. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **45**, 2189–2208.
- 849 Sévellec, F., and T. Huck, 2016: Geostrophic closure of the zonally-averaged atlantic merid-
850 ional overturning circulation. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **46**, 895–917.
- 851 Sévellec, F., T. Huck, and M. Ben Jelloul, 2006: On the mechanism of centennial thermo-
852 haline oscillations. *J. Mar. Res.*, **64**, 355–392.
- 853 Sévellec, F., N. Kolodziejczyk, Q. Jamet, and A. Colin de Verdière, 2025a: Global observa-
854 tions of eddy-mean flow interactions at the ocean surface and in the deep ocean. *J. Phys.*
855 *Oceanogr.*, **55**, 1569–1590.
- 856 Sévellec, F., N. Kolodziejczyk, and E. Portela, 2025b: Turbulent isopycnal mixing dominates
857 thermohaline transformations of intermediate ocean waters. *Nat. Commun.*, **16**, 9838.
- 858 Sévellec, F., A. Naveira Garabato, and T. Huck, 2021: Damping of climate-scale oceanic
859 variability by mesoscale eddy turbulence. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **51**, 491–503.
- 860 Small, R. J., and Coauthors, 2008: Air-sea interaction over ocean fronts and eddies. *Dyn.*
861 *Atmos. Oceans*, **45**, 274–319.
- 862 Starr, V. P., 1968: Physics of negative viscosity. *McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York*,
863 pp. 256.
- 864 Talley, L. D., G. L. Pickard, W. J. Emery, and J. H. Swift, 2011: Descriptive physical
865 oceanography: An introduction (sixth edition). *Elsevier*, 560 pp.
- 866 Taylor, G. I., 1921: Diffusion by continuous movements. *Proc. London Math. Soc.*, **20**, 196–
867 212.
- 868 Tomita, H., K. Kunio, K. Masahisa, and H. Tsutomu, 2021: Advances in the estimation of
869 global surface net heat flux based on satellite observation: J-ofuro3 v1.1. *Front. Mar. Sci.*,
870 **8**, 612361.

- 871 von Schuckmann, K., and Coauthors, 2023: Heat stored in the Earth system 1960–2020:
872 where does the energy go? *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, **15**, 1675–1709.
- 873 Walin, G., 1982: On the relation between sea-surface heat flow and thermal circulation in
874 the ocean. *Tellus*, **34**, 187–195.
- 875 Wunsch, C., 2011: The decadal mean ocean circulation and Sverdrup balance. *J. Mar. Res.*,
876 **69**, 417–434.
- 877 Yan, X., D. Kang, E. N. Curchitser, and C. Pang, 2019: Energetics of eddy-mean flow
878 interactions along the western boundary currents in the North Pacific. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*,
879 **49**, 789–810.
- 880 Zika, J. D., M. H. England, and W. P. Sijp, 2012: The ocean circulation in thermohaline
881 coordinates. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **42**, 708–724.
- 882 Zika, J. D., N. Skliris, A. J. G. Nurser, S. A. Josey, L. Mudryk, F. Laliberté, and R. Marsh,
883 2015: Maintenance and broadening of the ocean’s salinity distribution by the water cycle.
884 *J. Climate*, **28**, 9550–9560.